

Nitration of 2,3-Bis(*o*-Methoxyphenyl)-6-Hydroxy Benzofuran Derivatives

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Condensation of resorcinol and *o*-anisoin gave 2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-6-hydroxy benzofuran (1a) which yielded the 5,7-dinitro derivative (6a) upon nitration. Oxidation of its acetoxy derivative (6b) furnished 4-acetoxy-2-methoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone-2-*o*-anisate(7a). Hydrolysis of the latter compound gave 2,4-dihydroxy-2-methoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone(7b). Nitration of 6-methoxy-2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl) benzofuran (1b) gave a mixture of the 5-nitro derivative 3a together with a dinitro compound, namely 6-methoxy-5-nitro-2-(2-methoxy-4-nitrophenyl)-3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl) benzofuran(3b). The latter compound upon oxidation followed by hydrolysis gave 2,4-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone (5).

THE present communication describes a convenient method for obtaining substituted benzophenones which are otherwise difficultly accessible.

The reaction of *o*-anisoin and resorcinol in dioxan, in presence of hydrochloric acid furnished 2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-6-hydroxybenzofuran (1a). Acylation of 1a gave the 6-acetoxy derivative 1c which on oxidation with chromic-acetic acid mixture followed by alkaline hydrolysis of the ester 2d yielded 2,4-dihydroxy-2-methoxybenzophenone (2b). Methylation of the latter gave 2,2',4-trimethoxybenzophenone (2c) and its identity was established on the basis of the mixture m.p. with authentic sample. These observations supported the assigned structure of 1a. Methylation of 1a with dimethylsulphate in potassium hydroxide solution yielded its methyl ether 1b. Oxidation of 1b followed by hydrolysis of the resulting ester 2d gave 2',4-dimethoxy-2-hydroxybenzophenone-2e), which gave after methylation 2c. This was found to be identical with an authentic sample.

- a, R = H
b, R = OCH₃
c, R = COCH₃

- a, R = COC₆H₄OCH₃-O
R' = COCH₃
b, R = R' = H
c, R = R' = CH₃
d, R = COC₆H₄OCH₃-O,
R' = CH₃
e, R = H, R' = CH₃

Nitration of 1b with nitric acid in acetic acid gave a mixture of mono and dinitro derivatives, which were separated by fractional crystallisation. The presence of one nitro group in the phenyl ring at

position 2 in compound 3b was supported by oxidation of the compound followed by hydrolysis of the resulting ester 4b leading to the formation of 2',4-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone(5). The latter compound (5) was also obtained by hydrolysis of 4a which was formed by oxidation of 3a (m.p. and mixed m.p.).

Nitration of 2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-6-hydroxybenzofuran(1a) with nitric acid in acetic acid furnished the 5,7-dinitroderivative 6a. Acylation of 6a gave the acetoxy derivative 6b, which on

It is interest to note that Usgaoukar and Jadav⁸ reported a.m.p. 247-48° for compound 2b, whereas the present investigation showed that the m.p. is 175°.

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oxidation with chromic-acetic acid yielded 4-acetoxy-2'-methoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone-2-*o*-anisate (7a). The latter compound (7a), on hydrolysis gave 2,4-dihydroxy-2'-methoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone (7b).

Methylation of 6a with dimethyl sulphate yielded the 6-methoxy-derivative 6c, which upon oxidation followed by hydrolysis gave of 2', 4-dimethoxy-3,5-dinitro-2-hydroxybenzophenone (6d).

- 6
a, R = H
b, R = COCH₃⁻
c, R = CH₃

- 7
a, R = *o*-OCH₃C₆H₄,
R' = COCH₃⁻
b, R = R' = H
c, R = *o*-OCH₃C₆H₄,
R' = CH₃
d, R = H, R' = CH₃

Experimental

Melting points were not corrected. P.M.R. were obtained at 60 MHz in CDCl₃, with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were run at 70 ev. The infra-red spectra were carried out in potassium bromide on a Unicam infra-red spectrophotometer model SP 1000.

Preparation of 2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-6-hydroxybenzofuran (1a) :

A mixture of *o*-anisoin⁶ (1 g), resorcinol (2 g) in dioxan (25 ml), and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured onto ice (100 ml) and the resulting oil taken up in ether, the ethereal layer was washed with water and twice with 8% sodium hydroxide solution (50 ml). The alkaline solution was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid so obtained was successively recrystallized from benzene giving 1a as colourless needles, m.p. 195° : yield is ca (65%).

Analysis : for C₂₂H₁₈O₄, Calcd : C, 76.30 ; H, 5.20, Found : C, 76.77 ; H, 4.86%.

Preparation of 6-methoxy-2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-benzofuran (1b) :

To a solution of 7.5 g of 1a in 36 ml of potassium hydroxide solution (20%), 18.9 ml of dimethylsulphate was added.

The reaction mixture was shaken vigorously, after 10 minutes another 36 ml of potassium hydroxide solution and 18.9 ml of dimethylsulphate was added and the shaking continued for another 5 minutes. The reaction mixture was left for one hour at room temperature, then it was diluted with water, extracted with ether, washed with 5% potassium hydroxide solution, then with water and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After evaporation of the ether, a yellow oil was obtained

which was crystallized from ethanol to give 1b as colourless crystals, m.p. 50° , yield is ca 70%.

Analysis : for C₂₈H₂₀O₄, Calcd : C, 76.66 ; H, 5.55, Found : C, 76.40 ; H, 5.48%.

6-Acetoxy-2,3-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl)benzofuran (1c) :

A mixture of 1 g of 1a and 0.5 g of anhydrous sodium acetate in 10 ml of acetic anhydride was heated on a water bath for 3 hrs, then filtered while hot and left to cool. The separated crystals were filtered off and recrystallized from ethanol to give 70% of 1c as colourless platelets, m.p. 127°.

Analysis : for C₃₄H₂₀O₇, Calcd : C, 74.23 ; H, 5.15, Found : C, 74.54 ; H, 5.01%.

4-Acetoxy-2'-methoxybenzophenone-2-*o*-anisate (2a) :

To a hot solution of 0.4 g of chromic anhydride in 20 ml of glacial acetic acid was added 0.4 g of 1c. The mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes and poured onto water (20 ml), then left to cool. The solid so separated was filtered and crystallized from petrol. ether (b. p. 60-80°) yielding 2a as colourless crystals, m.p. 73-74° ; yield is ca 65%.

Analysis : for C₂₄H₂₀O₇, Calcd : C, 68.57 ; H, 4.76 ; Found : C, 68.42 ; H, 4.62%.

max 1650 (C=O), 1725 (anisate C=O) and 1765 cm⁻¹ (acetate C=O)

2,4-Dihydroxy-2'-methoxybenzophenone (2b) :

2,4-Dihydroxy-2'-methoxybenzophenone (2b) was obtained by refluxing 1g of 2a with 0.25 g of potassium hydroxide in 50 ml of ethanol for one hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated to about 10 ml, poured onto water, and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid so formed was filtered off to give 66% of 2b as colourless needles from petrol. ether (b.p. 40-60°), m.p. 175°. It gave a blood-red colouration with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Analysis : for C₁₄H₁₀O₄, Calcd : C, 68.85 ; H, 4.92 ; Found : C, 68.68 ; H, 4.60%.

max 1665 (C=O), 3170 cm⁻¹ (OH). Low resolution m.s m/e M⁺ 244 (12), 229(10), 213(40), 137 (100) and 107(90).

2,2',4-trimethoxybenzophenone (2c) :

Methylation of 2b (1 g) with dimethylsulphate as in the case of 1a gave (b.p. 40-60°), m.p. 57° ; in 50% yield. Melting point and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample⁸ showed no depression.

2,4-Dimethoxy-2-hydroxybenzophenone (2e) :

Oxidation of 1 g of 1b with chromic-acetic mixture as previously mentioned in the case of 2e gave 2d as colourless oil which was purified by petrol. ether (b.p. 40-60°) ; in 55% yield.

The oily compound 2d was hydrolysed with potassium hydroxide in ethanol to give 2-hydroxy-2',4-dimethoxybenzophenone (2c) as colourless crystals from ethanol, m.p. 80° ; yield ca 50%. It gave a red colour with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Analysis : for $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$, Calcd : C, 69.77 ; H, 4.43 ; Found : C, 69.86, H, 4.40%.

The infra-red spectrum of 2e showed a band at 1635 cm^{-1} (C=O) and a broad band at 3050 cm^{-1} (OH). Methylation of 2e with dimethylsulphate gave 60% of 2,2',4-trimethoxybenzophenone(2c) as colourless needles from petrol. ether (b.p. $40-60^\circ$), (m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previously prepared compound gave no depression).

Nitration of 6-methoxy-2,3-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)-benzofuran :

A suspension of 1 g of 6-methoxy-2,3-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)benzofuran(1b) in 2.5 ml of glacial acetic acid was treated with 0.46 ml of nitric acid and 0.5 ml of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° for 5 minutes, then poured onto water (20 ml), filtered and washed with water. The solid so obtained was crystallized from ethanol which afforded 6-methoxy-2,3-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)-5-nitrobenzofuran(3a) as pale yellow needles, m.p. 148° ; yield ca 30%.

Analysis : for $C_{22}H_{18}O_5N$, Calcd : C, 68.15 ; H, 4.69 ; N, 3.45 ; Found : C, 68.32 ; H, 4.75 ; N, 3.10%.

The insoluble compound was crystallized from acetone to give 6-methoxy-2-(2-methoxy-4-nitrophenyl)-3-(o-methoxyphenyl)-5-nitrobenzofuran(3b), as orange needles in 60% yield, m.p. 227° .

Analysis : for $C_{28}H_{18}O_8N_2$, Calcd : C, 61.33 ; H, 4.02 ; N, 6.22 ; Found : C, 61.20 ; H, 4.40 ; N, 5.90%.

Low resolution m.s., m/e M^+ 450(100), 435(5.23), 425(6.32), 4.5(15.38), 390(3.01), 375(3.45) and 360(1.89).

2'-4-Dimethoxy-5-nitrobenzophenone-2-(4-nitro-o-anisate) (4b) :

Oxidation of 0.4 of 3b with chromic-acetic acid mixture give 4b as yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 190° , in 70% yield.

Analysis : for $C_{28}H_{18}N_2O_{10}$, Calcd : C, 57.26 ; H, 3.73 ; N, 5.81 ; Found : C, 56.80 ; H, 3.80 ; N, 5.73%.

Low resolution m.s. M^+ , m/e (482), 451(5.28), 406(3.85), 272(11.90), 181(10.08) and 180(100). High resolution m.s., found : m/s 482.0966 ; Calcd for $C_{28}H_{18}N_2O_{10}$: 482.0971. $\max 1670$ (C=O) and 1765 cm^{-1} (C=O, ester).

2',4-Dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone(5) :

Hydrolysis of 1 g of 3b with alcoholic potassium hydroxide gave 75% of 2'-4-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone(5) as pale yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 155° . It gave a blood red colour with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Analysis : for $C_{15}H_{10}O_6N$, Calcd : C, 59.41 ; H, 4.29 ; N, 4.62 ; Found : C, 59.01 ; H, 4.17 ; N, 4.73%.

Low resolution m.s. m/e M^+ 303(6.08), 288(5.61), 272(100), 241(3.25), 225(10.38), 196(11.51) and 135(31.29). $\max 1630$ (C=O) and 3090 cm^{-1} (OH).

2'-4-Dimethoxy-5-nitrobenzophenone-2-o-anisate(4a) :

Compound 4a was prepared by oxidation of 0.4 g of 3a as previously described and the product was crystallised from ethanol yielding pale yellow needles, m.p. 142° , yield : ca 65%.

Analysis : for $C_{22}H_{18}O_5N$. Calcd : C, 63.15 ; H, 4.37 ; N, 3.20 ; Found : C, 63.32 ; H, 4.41 ; N, 3.42%. $\max 1650$ (C=O) and 1765 cm^{-1} (C=O ester).

Hydrolysis of 1 g of the compound 4a with potassium hydroxide in ethanol, gave 2'-4-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzophenone(5) as pale yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 155° ; yield : ca 60%. M.p. and mixed m.p. with the previously prepared compound gave no depression.

5-7-Dinitro-2,3-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)-6-hydroxy-benzofuran(6a) :

A suspension of 1g of 2,3-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)-6-hydroxybenzofuran(1a) in 2.5 ml of glacial acetic acid was nitrated with a mixture of 0.46 ml of nitric acid and 0.5 ml of glacial acetic acid. The product was crystallized from ethanol and gave 60% of 6a as orange crystals, m.p. 197° .

Analysis : for $C_{22}H_{18}O_8N_2$, Calcd : C, 60.55 ; H, 3.76 ; N, 6.42 ; Found : C, 60.60 ; H, 3.70 ; N, 5.94%.

P.M.R. ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.40(3H, OCH_3 , s), 3.72(3H, OCH_3 , a), 8.40(1H, C-4, a) and 8.88-7.56(8H, aromatic, m). Low resolution m.s. m/e M^+ 436(8), 406(100), 376(40) and 344(35). $\max 3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH).

6-Acetoxy-5,7-dinitro-2,3-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)benzofuran(6b) :

A mixture of 1 g of 6a in 10 ml of acetic anhydride and 0.5 g of anhydrous sodium acetate was refluxed for 3 hrs, and left to cool. The precipitated material was filtered off and recrystallized from ethanol to give 6b as golden yellow needles, m.p. 192° ; yield is ca 80%.

Analysis : for $C_{24}H_{18}O_9N_2$, Calcd : C, 60.26 ; H, 3.76 ; N, 5.86 ; Found : C, 60.00 ; H, 4.10 ; N, 5.35%.

P.M.R. ($CDCl_3$) δ 2.44(3H, $COCH_3$, m), 3.76(3H, OCH_3 , s) 8.40(1H, C-4, a) and 6.90-7.58(8H, aromatic, m).

Low resolution m.s. m/e M^+ 478(7.70), 436(100), 344(28.08) and 135(75.60). $\max 1790\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O, ester).

4-Acetoxy-2'-methoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone-2-o-anisate(7a) :

Compound 6b (0.4 g) was oxidised with chromic acid mixture to give 60% of 7a as yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 177° .

Analysis : for $C_{24}H_{18}O_{11}N_2$, Calcd : C, 56.47 ; H, 3.53 ; N, 5.49 ; Found : C, 56.54 ; H, 3.90 ; N, 5.62%. $\max 1635$ (C=O), 1740 (C=O, ester) and 1790 cm^{-1} (C=O, acetoxy).

2,4-Dihydroxy-3,5-dinitro-2'-methoxybenzophenone(7b) :

Hydrolysis of 1 g of 7a by refluxing with a solution of potassium hydroxide (0.25) in ethanol

(50 ml) for one hour, yielded after concentration and acidification 55% of 7b as orange needles from ethanol, m.p. 280°.

It gave a blood red colour with ferric chloride solution.

Analysis : for $C_{14}H_{10}O_8N_2$, Calcd : C, 50.29 ; H, 2.99 ; N, 8.38 ; Found : C, 50.54 ; H, 3.32 ; N, 8.54%. \max 1645(C=O) and 3100 cm^{-1} (OH).

6-Methoxy-2,5-bis-(o-methoxyphenyl)-5,7-dinitro-benzofuran(6c) :

To a solution of 1 g of 6a in 5 ml of potassium hydroxide (20%) was added 2.5 ml of dimethyl-sulphate. The reaction mixture was well stirred and then filtered after cooling. The product was crystallized from ethanol to give orange needles, m.p. 159°, yield : ca 60%.

Analysis : for $C_{23}H_{18}N_2O_8$, Calcd : C, 61.35 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 6.22 ; Found : C, 61.20 ; H, 3.80 ; N, 5.93%.

P.M.R. ($CDCl_3$) δ 3.38(3H, OCH_3 , s), 3.70(3H, OCH_3 , s), 4.06(3H, OCH_3 , s), 8.18(1H, C-4, s) and 6.88-7.58(8H, aromatic m). Low resolution m.s. m/e M^+ 450(100), 435(9.79), 420(6.20), 405(9.61) and 135(16.82).

2'-4-Dimethoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone-2-o-anisate (7c) :

In a similar manner as in case of 2a, oxidation of 0.4 g of 6c with chromic-acetic acid mixture 7c was formed as yellow needles from ethanol in 45% yield, m.p. 176°.

Analysis : for $C_{25}H_{18}O_{10}N_2$, Calcd : C, 57.26 ; H, 3.73 ; N, 5.81 ; Found : C, 56.98 ; H, 3.92 ; N, 5.67%. \max 1635(C=O) and 1780 cm^{-1} (C=O, ester).

2-Hydroxy-2',4-dimethoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone (7d) :

Hydrolysis of 1 g of 7c with potassium hydroxide in ethanol gave 60% of 7d as yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 120°. It gave a blood red colour with aqueous ferric chloride solution.

Analysis : for $C_{15}H_{12}O_8N_2$, Calcd : C, 51.72 ; H, 3.45 ; N, 8.04 ; Found : C, 51.91 ; H, 3.56 ; N, 8.32%. \max 1645 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Discussion

The p.m.r.⁴ spectrum of 1a($CDCl_3$) showed a hydroxy proton at δ 4.85 as singlet (1H), which

disappeared after adding D_2O , and two OCH_3 protons at δ 3.38 s(3H) and 3.59 s(3H). The spectrum revealed also the presence of 11 aromatic protons with chemical shifts at δ 6.65-7.48 as multiplets. The infra-red⁵ spectrum of 1a showed a broad band at 3250 cm^{-1} (OH).

On the other hand, the p.m.r. of 1b showed signals at δ 3.32 s(3H, OCH_3), 3.58 s(3H, OCH_3), 3.72 s(3H, OCH_3) and 6.75-7.56 m(11H, aromatic). The OH band present in the ir spectrum of 1a at 3250 cm^{-1} was absent in the ir spectrum of 1b. The ir spectrum of 1c showed an ester stretch at 1770 cm^{-1} .

Comparison of the p.m.r. spectra of the compounds 3b, 4b and 5 revealed the presence of signals at δ 8.04, in 3b, s(1H, C-4), 8.22 in 4b s(1H, C-6) and 8.08 in 5 s(1H, C-6). The signal caused by the proton on C-7 in 3b appeared at δ 7.22 as singlet. Meanwhile, the singlet signals due to C-3 in both 4b and 5 appeared at δ 7.02 and 6.59, respectively; this upfield shift is attributed to the presence of an OH group in the o-position⁴. Singlet signals at δ 7.94 (C-3 of the phenyl group at position 2 in 3b) and δ 7.80 (C-3 of the anisate group in 4b) were also observed. This lends an additional support for the presence of one nitro group at C-4 of the phenyl at position 2 in 3b and C-4 of the anisate group in 4b. The p.m.r. of 3b showed also 3 OCH_3 as singlets at δ 3.44, 3.64 and 4.04, and 7 aromatic protons as a multiplet at (7.2-7.60). Three OCH_3 groups in compound 4b at δ 3.56, 3.76 and 4.00, also 7 aromatic protons appeared at δ 7.08-7.78 m. The p.m.r. showed only two OCH_3 groups at δ 3.82 and 4.02 and 4 aromatic protons at 6.92-7.7 as multiplets.

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